

**Network of Inclusive COVEs on Circular
Material Welding and Preventive
Maintenance for Socially Safe, Resilient &
Sustainable Automotive Manufacturing**

**Deliverable D7.1: Dissemination, Exploitation &
Communication Plan**

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Erasmus+ Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101193814

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